

Reactions of Protonic Acids with Benzanthrone and Dibenzylanthrone

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Reactions of protonic acids with benzanthrone and dibenzylanthrone have been studied in nitrobenzene using electrochemical and thermochemical techniques. These ketones have been successfully titrated against various acids conductometrically and potentiometrically and it has been inferred that the ketone-protonic acid adducts are ionic in nature. However, the titrations of acetic, mono chloroacetic and dichloroacetic acids with these ketones have not been successful indicating that their interactions with these ketones are relatively weak. Heats of reactions of these ketones with various acids have been found to vary with concentration and the acid strength has been found to decrease in the following orders :

Whereas the complexes of ketones with Lewis acids have been studied in detail¹⁻³, very little is known about their reactions with protonic acids⁴. It is because of the insolubility of protonic acids in all common non-polar solvents which are suitable for study of the addition complexes of Lewis acids with ketones. In the present communication, an attempt has been made to study the reactions of benzanthrone and 10,10-dibenzylanthrone with sulphuric, disulphuric, fluorosulphuric, chlorosulphuric, hydrochloric, hydrobromic, trichloroacetic, dichloroacetic, monochloroacetic and acetic acids in nitrobenzene using electrochemical and thermochemical techniques.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzanthrone², 10,10-dibenzylanthrone⁵, fluorosulphuric acid⁶, substituted acetic acids and nitrobenzene⁷ were prepared and/or purified according to the procedures reported in literature. Chlorosulphuric acid (BDH) was distilled at 149°/740 mm. using a small fractionating column. Anhydrous sulphuric acid was prepared by distilling calculated amount of sulphur trioxide into a known amount of sulphuric acid (A.R.). Disulphuric acid was prepared by a similar procedure from 100% sulphuric acid. The purity of the acids was then checked by analytical methods. Dry hydrochloric and hydrobromic acid gases were dissolved in nitrobenzene and the solutions were standardised by estimating the halogen content.

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For conductometric titrations, known quantity of ketone solution in nitrobenzene was taken in the conductivity cell and the resistance was measured. The standard acid solution was added in small lots and change in conductance noted. Specific conductance was then plotted against concentration represented by acid/base molar ratio.

For potentiometric titrations, a fibre type standard calomel electrode was used as reference electrode and platinum electrode as hydrogen ion indicator electrode. The potential was measured with portable (Pye) potentiometer (Cat. No. 7569-P). The null point was detected by an external scalamp galvanometer.

Heats of reactions were measured using an isothermal phase change calorimeter with diphenyl ether as the dilatometric fluid (m.p. 26.9°). The procedure was the same as reported earlier⁸. The enthalpy of reactions was calculated as heat evolved per mole of the acid neutralised, base being taken in excess. The maximum probable error in these measurements is less than 1%.

DISCUSSION

The choice of a suitable solvent for these studies has been difficult as these protonic acids do not dissolve in common inert solvents and various sulphuric acids react with benzene. Solvents such as ethyl acetate, acetone, dimethylformamide and methanol are more basic than dibenzylanthrone and benzanthrone⁹ and will themselves react with the acids in preference to these ketones. Acyl halides which were used for the separation of the complexes of these anthrones with Lewis acids^{1,2} have been found to be decomposed by the protonic acids. Nitrobenzene has been employed as a solvent in these studies as it is a much weaker donor than the anthrones⁹ and dissolves the acids and the bases. Their solutions are quite stable in nitrobenzene.

No adduct of those ketones with the acids could be isolated. An attempt to separate the adducts by saturating the ketone solutions in carbon tetrachloride with hydrohalic acids also proved unsuccessful. However, there is a clear indication of complex formation as the colour of benzanthrone solution changed from yellow to red. It may be stated that the anthrones usually impart a red colour to acid solutions in non-aqueous solvents and the colour change is so sharp in case of benzanthrone that it has been used as an indicator in acid base titrations¹⁰. As no adduct could be isolated, conductance, potentiometric and thermochemical studies in nitrobenzene have been carried out with a view to elucidate the behaviour of protonic acids towards these ketones.

Conductance studies : Dibenzylanthrone and benzanthrone dissolve in nitrobenzene giving non-conducting solutions. However, trichloroacetic, dichloroacetic, hydrochloric, hydrobromic and substituted sulphuric acids have been found to give conducting solutions in nitrobenzene suggesting that the acids form solvates with nitrobenzene which are polar in character⁷. Conductance of solutions of acetic and monochloroacetic acids in nitrobenzene indicates that these acids are very weak and do not ionise in it. Conductometric titrations

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of these ketones with various protonic acids have, therefore, been carried out in nitrobenzene in order to determine the stoichiometry of the adducts (Fig. 1, 2). The titrations with dichloroacetic, monochloroacetic and acetic acids have not been successful indicating that they do not form adducts with these ketones. The titration curves with disulphuric and sulphuric acids exhibit two breaks corresponding to acid/base molar ratios of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2. In all other cases there is only one inflexion corresponding to acid/base molar ratio of 1 : 1.

It may, therefore, be concluded that disulphuric and sulphuric acids act as dibasic acids whereas all other acids act as monobasic acids. The reactions between the ketones (B) and a monobasic acid (HA) may be represented as :

Similarly the reactions with a dibasic acid (H_2A) may be written as :

It is evident from these titrations that the adducts are ionic in character and probably exist as ion pairs in equilibrium with respective ions.

Potentiometric titrations: : The stoichiometry of the adducts of dibenzylanthrone and benzanthrone with substituted sulphuric acids has been further supported by carrying out potentiometric titrations in nitrobenzene. E.m.f. has been plotted against acid/base molar ratio and the curves are presented in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 3. Potentiometric titrations of protonic acids with benzanthrone in nitrobenzene at 26°C

The curves show a fair change in e.m.f. at acid/base molar ratio of 1 : 1 with mono-basic acids and at molar ratios of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 with dibasic acids which may be explained on the basis of the reactions given here.

Thermochemical measurements: Heats of reactions of these protonic acids with benzanthrone and dibenzylanthrone have been measured in nitrobenzene with a view to determine the relative acceptor strengths of these acids and the donor strengths of the ketones. The values are presented in Tables I and II. The mode of reactions is essentially the same

TABLE I

Heats of reactions ($-\Delta H$) of protonic acids with benzanthrone in nitrobenzene (25 ml)

Protonic acids	Amount of acid g.mole $\times 10^{-4}$	Molar ratio acid : base	$-\Delta H$ kcal/mole
$H_2S_2O_7$	3.81	1 : 4.0	42.0
	3.02	1 : 5.0	43.2
	2.74	1 : 5.5	43.5
	2.31	1 : 6.6	44.4
	1.51	1 : 10.1	45.0
H_2SO_4	7.66	1 : 3.4	8.8
	6.02	1 : 4.3	9.0
	4.58	1 : 5.7	9.1
	3.10	1 : 8.4	9.4
	2.06	1 : 12.6	9.8
HSO_3F	5.41	1 : 2.8	26.5
	4.00	1 : 3.8	26.9
	2.33	1 : 6.5	27.8
	1.69	1 : 9.0	28.1
	1.12	1 : 13.5	28.4
HSO_3Cl	6.16	1 : 2.1	17.2
	5.42	1 : 2.4	19.8
	4.50	1 : 2.9	22.9
	3.91	1 : 3.3	24.8
	3.20	1 : 4.0	27.0

TABLE I - (Contd.)

Protonic acids	Amount of acid g.mole $\times 10^{-4}$	Molar ratio acid : base	$-\Delta H$ kcal/mole
HCl	4.20	1 : 3.9	4.5
	3.64	1 : 4.5	5.0
	1.84	1 : 8.9	5.2
	1.10	1 : 14.9	5.5
HBr	7.84	1 : 1.6	3.6
	6.52	1 : 1.9	4.1
	5.38	1 : 2.3	4.6
	4.42	1 : 2.8	5.1
CCl ₃ COOH	6.33	1 : 4.0	2.6
	4.01	1 : 6.3	2.6
	1.82	1 : 13.9	2.8
	1.02	1 : 25.0	2.9
CHCl ₂ COOH	6.80	1 : 3.2	1.3
	5.52	1 : 4.0	1.3
	2.78	1 : 7.9	1.5
CH ₂ ClCOOH	7.21	1 : 2.4	0.5
	6.93	1 : 2.5	0.7
	4.42	1 : 3.9	0.7

TABLE II

Heats of reactions ($-\Delta H$) of protonic acids with dibenzylanthrone in nitrobenzene (25 ml)

Protonic acid	Amount of acid g.mole $\times 10^{-4}$	Molar ratio acid : base	$-\Delta H$ kcal/mole
H ₂ S ₂ O ₇	8.01	1 : 2.9	23.1
	6.82	1 : 3.4	24.2
	5.03	1 : 4.6	25.8
	4.21	1 : 5.6	26.5
	3.52	1 : 6.9	27.3
H ₂ SO ₄	8.16	1 : 2.9	7.5
	6.00	1 : 3.9	8.4
	5.85	1 : 4.0	8.6
	4.30	1 : 5.5	9.1
HSO ₃ F	7.50	1 : 2.2	17.8
	7.00	1 : 2.4	19.0
	5.27	1 : 3.2	22.4
	3.19	1 : 5.2	25.5
HSO ₃ Cl	7.81	1 : 1.2	10.9
	6.49	1 : 1.5	16.5
	5.52	1 : 1.7	19.6
	5.03	1 : 1.9	22.5
HCl	6.50	1 : 1.7	2.8
	5.98	1 : 1.8	3.6
	5.02	1 : 2.1	4.4
	4.33	1 : 2.5	5.2
HBr	7.42	1 : 1.4	2.6
	6.48	1 : 1.6	3.7
	5.73	1 : 1.8	4.1
	4.64	1 : 2.2	4.5
CCl ₃ COOH	7.21	1 : 3.9	2.4
	6.08	1 : 4.6	2.5
	3.86	1 : 7.2	2.7
	2.46	1 : 11.3	2.8

as reported under conductance studies. The values of the heats of reactions show a marked decrease with increase in the concentration of the acid. Heats of solution of protonic acids in nitrobenzene have indicated that the acids are not completely ionised at all concentrations and are better ionised at lower concentrations. This results in higher heat of solvation at lower concentrations⁸. It is therefore, expected that the heat of reaction will vary with change in concentration of the acid. Heat is likely to be absorbed as more and more of the acid-nitrobenzene adduct dissociates as the reaction approaches completion. On the basis of the enthalpy values obtained, the relative orders of the strengths of these protonic acids towards benzanthrone and dibenzylanthrone are as follows :

which are supported by the studies of these acids in dimethylformamide¹¹ and acetic acid¹². The strengths of dibasic acids have not been compared with those of the monobasic acids as it is not advisable to take the average heat of solvation of a proton where two protons are available for solvation.

The neutralisation reactions of dichloroacetic, monochloroacetic and acetic acids with dibenzylanthrone and of acetic acid with benzanthrone in nitrobenzene do not result in any measurable heat change. Even the heats of neutralisation of dichloroacetic and trichloroacetic acids with benzanthrone have been found to be much lower than those with other protonic acids. The order of relative strengths of substituted acetic acids towards these ketones appears to be as follows :

which is reasonable as the acid strength is expected to increase with replacement of hydrogen atom of methyl group with chlorine.

It is also evident from these studies that benzanthrone is a stronger base than dibenzylanthrone. Benzanthrone is expected to be a better donor as its π molecular orbital is common to the whole ring system whereas benzene rings in dibenzylanthrone act as electron sinks and reduce the donor ability of its carbonyl oxygen considerably.

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